

HASHING ALGORITHMS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Hash functions are fundamental mechanisms in contemporary computing, widely employed in data structures, indexing, and security systems. This paper presents a comparative analysis between two distinct approaches to string hashing functions: one based on linear weighting (successive additions) and another based on successive multiplication inspired by the classic DJB2 algorithm. The methodology combines the structural mathematical modeling of the algorithms with an empirical validation conducted in the C++ programming language, exhaustively testing all possible four-letter uppercase combinations mapped into in-memory hash tables (unordered_map). The results demonstrate that while the linear model exhibits strict linear growth, low sensitivity to character ordering (vulnerability to anagrams), and a high collision rate, the DJB2 algorithm distributes data significantly more uniformly and drastically mitigates the occurrence of collisions due to its geometric and multiplicative behavior. It is concluded that minor modifications in mathematical modeling directly impact bit space utilization and computational efficiency, highlighting the logical rigor required in teaching and designing data structures.

Keywords: Hashing algorithms, comparative analysis, hash function, collision rate.

1. INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM DEFINITION

In the development of computer systems, dispersion functions (hashing) are widely used to transform textual or numerical information into compact, fixed-size values. This type of processing is present in several areas of computing, including:

- ◆ data structures;
- ◆ search engines;
- ◆ record indexing;
- ◆ user authentication;
- ◆ password storage;
- ◆ digital signatures;
- ◆ file integrity verification;
- ◆ cryptographic systems.

A hash function receives a variable-size input, usually a character string, and produces a numerical value associated with that information. The primary objective consists of distributing data efficiently within the available numerical space, thereby reducing the occurrence of collisions.

The phenomenon known as a collision occurs when two different inputs produce the same hash result. Although collisions are inevitable in any finite numerical representation system, well-designed dispersion functions seek to minimize their incidence and distribute the results uniformly.

In this presentation, two distinct implementation approaches are mathematically analyzed:

- ◆ a version based on linear weighting;
- ◆ a version based on successive multiplication using the DJB2 algorithm.

The analysis compares the structural behavior of both implementations, observing aspects related to numerical distribution, bit space utilization, and collision incidence.

2. DETAILED ANALYSIS: VERSION 1 (LINEAR WEIGHTING)

```
static std::string myHash(std::string mensagem) {
    unsigned long hashCalculated = 0;
    unsigned int peso = 1;

    for (char c : mensagem) {
        hashCalculated += static_cast<unsigned long>(c) * peso;
        peso++;
    }

    std::stringstream hash;
    hash << std::setfill('0') << std::setw(10) << hashCalculated;
    return hash.str();
}
```

The first implementation utilizes a strategy based on a weighted sum of characters. Each symbol of the input string is converted to its corresponding ASCII value and multiplied by an increasing weight according to its position within the sequence.

The result of these multiplications is accumulated in a numerical variable named hashCalculated, which is responsible for the final composition of the hash.

The processing occurs as follows:

"ABC"

o processamento ocorre da seguinte forma:

Character	ASCII	Weight	Result
A	65	1	65
B	66	2	132
C	67	3	201

The final value corresponds to the summation of the results:

$$65 + 132 + 201 = 398$$

Mathematically, the behavior of the function can be represented by the following expression (Equation 1):

$$\text{Hash}(S) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{ASCII}(S_i) \times (i + 1) \quad (1)$$

Where:

- S represents the input character string.
- n is the total length of the string (number of characters).
- S_i represents the individual character located at index i (zero-based).
- $\text{ASCII}(S_i)$ is the conversion of the character to its corresponding ASCII value.

Since the algorithm works exclusively with successive additions, the growth of the numerical value occurs in a linear fashion. Consequently, different combinations of characters can produce identical or very close results. This behavior significantly increases the occurrence of collisions.

Consider, for example, the following inputs:

```
"ABCD"
"ACBD"
```

Although the strings are different, small positional alterations produce only proportional changes in the final summation. Because the algorithm depends entirely on additive operations, its dispersion capacity remains limited.

Another important aspect is related to the utilization of the available numerical space. Although the *unsigned long* type supports high values, linear growth restricts the amplitude of the results produced by the algorithm.

The instruction `hash << std::setfill('0') << std::setw(10) << hashCalculated;` does not increase the mathematical dispersion of the hash. It merely formats the output visually, filling empty positions with leading zeros. Thus, a value such as **398** is displayed as **000000398** without any structural alteration.

3. DETAILED ANALYSIS: VERSION 2 (SUCCESSIVE MULTIPLICATIVE)

```
static std::string myHash(std::string mensagem) {
    unsigned long hashCalculated = 5381;

    for (char c : mensagem) {
        hashCalculated = ((hashCalculated * 33) + hashCalculated) + static_cast<unsigned long>(c);
    }

    std::stringstream hash;
    hash << std::setfill('0') << std::setw(10) << hashCalculated;
    return hash.str();
}
```

The second implementation uses a multiplicative approach inspired by the DJB2 algorithm, developed in the 1990s by computer scientist Dan Bernstein (Bernstein, n.d.). The

algorithm became widely known in dispersion applications due to its structural simplicity, low computational cost, and good numerical distribution for short and medium-length character strings (Bernstein, n.d.).

Unlike the previous linear version, the accumulated value of the hash does not grow solely through successive additions. At each iteration, the previous result directly participates in the next calculation through successive multiplications, significantly expanding the dispersion of the produced results.

The mathematical behavior of the function can be represented by the relation (Equation 2):

$$H_i = (H_{i-1} \times 33) + ASCII(S_i) \quad (2)$$

Where:

- H_i represents the current hash value.
- H_{i-1} represents the accumulated value from the previous step;
- $ASCII(S_i)$ corresponds to the character being processed.

In this approach, each new character modifies not only the current value but also influences all subsequent operations of the calculation.

Consider the inputs:

"ABCD"
"DCBA"

In the linear implementation, altering positions produces relatively small differences. Conversely, in the multiplicative implementation, changing the order of the characters completely modifies the sequence of multiplications performed during processing. This behavior significantly increases the dispersion of the results and reduces the incidence of collisions.

Another relevant aspect is related to the numerical space utilization. Since the algorithm performs successive multiplications, the accumulated value grows rapidly, utilizing a much larger range of the bits available in the *unsigned long* type. Consequently, the results present a wider and less predictable numerical distribution.

The initial constant 5381 and the multiplier 33 were empirically defined during the development of the DJB2 algorithm and present good dispersion behavior for character strings in general computing applications.

Although DJB2 exhibits significantly superior performance compared to the linear model for in-memory dispersion and data structures, it should not be used as a cryptographic algorithm for secure password storage (Moriarty et al., 2017; Biryukov et al., 2021).

Modern authentication systems utilize specific algorithms for credential protection, such as (Moriarty et al., 2017; Biryukov et al., 2021):

- ◆ bcrypt;
- ◆ Argon2;
- ◆ PBKDF2.

DJB2 belongs primarily to the context of computational dispersion and efficient data indexing.

4. COMPARATIVE TABLE

In order to consolidate the structural and behavioral differences between the two analyzed dispersion approaches, a set of cutting criteria was established to contrast everything from the arithmetic foundation to the practical impact on collision occurrence. Table 1 summarizes the comparative mapping between the Linear Weighting implementation (Version 1) and the Successive Multiplicative implementation based on the DJB2 algorithm (Version 2).

Table 1 – Structural and operational confrontation of the analyzed hashing algorithms.

Analysis Criterion	Version 1: Linear Weighting	Version 2: Multiplicative (DJB2)
Mathematical Structure	Weighted sum	Successive multiplication
Mathematical Behavior	Arithmetic Progression	Geometric Progression
Numerical Growth	Linear	Multiplicative
Sensitivity to Orde	Low	High
Bit Utilization	Limited	Wide
Collision Incidence	High	Reduced
Numerical Distribution	Restricted	More uniform
Iteration Formula	$H = H + (\text{ASCII} \times \text{weight})$	$H = (H \times 33) + \text{ASCII}$
Initial Value (Seed)	0 (Vulnerable to empty strings)	5381 (Dispersion Prime Number)
Anagram Resistance	Null ("AZ" and "ZA" generate collisions)	Excellent (Inversion changes the product)
Primary Application	Structural demonstration	Practical dispersion

From the data synthesized in Table 1, it is observed that the divergence in the performance of the functions does not stem from the complexity of the code itself, given that

both operate in linear time complexity $O(n)$ with respect to the input string length, but fundamentally from the nature of their arithmetic operations.

The inclusion of a multiplicative operation associated with a prime dispersion seed (5381) breaks the additive predictability of Version 1. While linear weighting severely fails in handling anagrams due to the commutative property masked by strictly arithmetic growth, the geometric iteration of Version 2 guarantees the avalanche effect, where the alteration of a single bit or character position completely reorganizes the composition of the significant bits in the output accumulator.

5. EMPIRICAL COLLISION ANALYSIS

The practical evaluation and statistical validation of both implementations were carried out through automated brute-force testing utilizing an exhaustive sample universe. In the test programs presented in the appendix, the algorithm combinatorially generates all possible variations of character strings with a fixed length of four positions ($n = 4$), restricted to the scope of the 26 uppercase letters of the Latin alphabet.

This type of analysis allows experimental observation of:

- ◆ result distribution;
- ◆ collision quantity;
- ◆ mathematical behavior of dispersion;
- ◆ structural efficiency of each approach.

In the linear implementation, the collision rate grows rapidly due to the limitation of the space effectively occupied by the results. In the DJB2 implementation, successive multiplication significantly expands numerical dispersion, drastically reducing the incidence of collisions within the same test suite.

Mathematically, the size of the dataset injected into the hash functions is determined by a permutation with repetition, totaling exactly $26^4 = 456,976$ tested strings.

This massive volume of data (nearly half a million records) guarantees the statistical weight of the experiment, allowing high-precision observation of each algorithm's dispersion behavior under stress. Each of the 456,976 generated strings was processed and mapped into an in-memory hash table structure, associating each calculated hash value with the vector of strings that originated it, enabling the exact count of collisions that occurred using the `std::unordered_map` resource.

6. CONCLUSION

The two implementations analyzed in this study use distinct arithmetic principles to transform character strings into identifying numerical values. The first version, grounded in a linear weighting strategy by successive additions, exhibits severe structural limitations. As evidenced in the modeling and exhaustive testing, its purely arithmetic growth

restricts dispersion amplitude and annuls anagram resistance, resulting in rapid saturation of the search space and a high collision rate.

In contrast, the version based on the classic DJB2 algorithm employs successive multiplications over the accumulated value of the hash, which significantly optimizes data distribution. By introducing a prime seed and geometric behavior, the algorithm achieves the avalanche effect, expanding the utilization of available bit space in the unsigned long type and drastically mitigating the incidence of collisions.

The confrontation between the two models, empirically validated by the exhaustive processing of 456,976 test vectors in a C++ environment, demonstrates how subtle modifications in the mathematical modeling of an algorithm produce drastic divergences in its computational efficiency, dispersion, bit space utilization, and numerical distribution uniformity. Ultimately, this work fulfills its educational and scientific purpose by highlighting the direct dependence relationship between the logical rigor of mathematical abstraction and the practical behavior of data structures essential to contemporary computing.

REFERENCES

Bernstein, D. J. (n.d.). DJB2 hash function.

Biryukov, A., Dinu, D., Khovratovich, D., & Josefsson, S. (2021). Argon2 memory-hard function for password hashing and proof-of-work applications (RFC 9106). Internet Engineering Task Force.

Moriarty, K., Kaliski, B., & Rusch, A. (2017). PKCS #5: Password-based cryptography specification version 2.1 (RFC 8018). Internet Engineering Task Force.

APPENDIX

Test programs for both versions using dispersion algorithms are presented below.

First version (linear weighting – collision 1)

```
// =====
// PROGRAM      : colisao1.cpp
// DESCRIPTION  : Script for empirical analysis and brute-force cracking.
//               Maps the behavior of the linear weighting hash function,
//               utilizing in-memory hash tables (unordered_map)
//               to quantify mathematical efficiency and collision rate.
// AUTHOR       : Prof. Me. José Augusto Navarro García Manzano
// VERSION      : 1.0
// DATE         : May / 2026
// GUIDELINES   : ISO/IEC - Logical and structural rigor for programming teaching.
// =====
#include <iostream>
#include <string>
#include <sstream>
#include <iomanip>
#include <unordered_map>
#include <vector>

using namespace std;

// The linear weighting function
string myHash(string mensagem) {
    unsigned long hashCalculated = 0, peso = 1;
    for (char c : mensagem) {
        hashCalculated += static_cast<unsigned long>(c) * peso;
        peso++;
    }
    stringstream hash;
    hash << std::setfill('0') << std::setw(10) << hashCalculated;
    return hash.str();
}

int main(void) {
    // Map that associates the generated Hash with the strings that produced it
    unordered_map<string, vector<string>> mapaDeHashes;

    // Simple string generator for testing (combinations of 4 uppercase characters)
    unsigned long totalStringsTestadas = 0, totalColisoes = 0;
    double taxaColisao;

    for (char c1 = 'A'; c1 <= 'Z'; c1++) {
        for (char c2 = 'A'; c2 <= 'Z'; c2++) {
            for (char c3 = 'A'; c3 <= 'Z'; c3++) {
                for (char c4 = 'A'; c4 <= 'Z'; c4++) {
                    string texto = "";
                    texto += c1;
                    texto += c2;
                    texto += c3;
                    texto += c4;

                    totalStringsTestadas++;
                    string h = myHash(texto);

                    // Stores the string in the vector corresponding to that hash
                    mapaDeHashes[h].push_back(texto);
                }
            }
        }
    }

    cout << "======" << endl;
    cout << "COLLISION TEST RESULT - VERSION 1.0" << endl;
    cout << "======" << endl;
    cout << "Total strings tested (size 4): " << totalStringsTestadas << endl;

    // Scans the map looking for vectors with a size greater than 1 (indicates collision)
    for (auto const& [hash, strings] : mapaDeHashes) {
        if (strings.size() > 1) {
```

```

totalColisoos += (strings.size() - 1);

// Displays the first 5 collisions found to avoid flooding the screen
if (totalColisoos <= 5) {
    cout << "Hash: [" << hash << "] collided for inputs: ";
    for (const string& s : strings) {
        cout << "\"" << s << "\" ";
    }
    cout << endl;
}
}
}

cout << "-----" << endl;
cout << "Total collisions detected: " << totalColisoos << endl;
taxaColisao = (static_cast<double>(totalColisoos) / totalStringsTestadas) * 100.0;
cout << "Collision rate within the tested scope: " << taxaColisao << "%" << endl;
cout << "======" << endl;

cout << endl << "Press <Enter> to exit... ";
cin.get();

return 0;
}

```

second version (multiplicative with prime constant – collision 2)

```

// =====
// PROGRAM      : colisao2.cpp
// DESCRIPTION   : Script for empirical analysis and statistical validation.
//               Maps the behavior of the multiplicative hash function of
//               successive constant (DJB2), visually demonstrating the effectiveness
//               of non-linear dispersion and the drastic reduction of collisions.
// AUTHOR       : Prof. Me. José Augusto Navarro Garcia Manzano
// VERSION      : 2.0
// DATE        : May / 2026
// GUIDELINES   : ISO/IEC - Logical and structural rigor for programming teaching.
// =====
#include <iostream>
#include <string>
#include <sstream>
#include <iomanip>
#include <unordered_map>
#include <vector>

using namespace std;

// The multiplicative function with a prime constant
static std::string myHash(std::string mensagem) {
    unsigned long hashCalculated = 5381;
    for (char c : mensagem)
        hashCalculated = ((hashCalculated * 33) + hashCalculated) + static_cast<unsigned long>(c);
    std::stringstream hash;
    hash << std::setfill('0') << std::setw(10) << hashCalculated;
    return hash.str();
}

int main(void) {
    // Map that associates the generated Hash with the strings that produced it
    unordered_map<string, vector<string>> mapaDeHashes;

    // Simple string generator for testing (combinations of 4 uppercase characters)
    unsigned long totalStringsTestadas = 0, totalColisoos = 0;
    double taxaColisao;

    for (char c1 = 'A'; c1 <= 'Z'; c1++) {
        for (char c2 = 'A'; c2 <= 'Z'; c2++) {
            for (char c3 = 'A'; c3 <= 'Z'; c3++) {
                for (char c4 = 'A'; c4 <= 'Z'; c4++) {
                    string texto = "";
                    texto += c1;
                    texto += c2;
                    texto += c3;
                    texto += c4;

                    totalStringsTestadas++;
                }
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

        string h = myHash(texto);

        // Stores the string in the vector corresponding to that hash
        mapaDeHashes[h].push_back(texto);
    }
}
}

cout << "=====" << endl;
cout << "COLLISION TEST RESULT - VERSION 2.0" << endl;
cout << "=====" << endl;
cout << "Total strings tested (size 4): " << totalStringsTestadas << endl;

// Scans the map looking for vectors with a size greater than 1 (indicates collision)
for (auto const& [hash, strings] : mapaDeHashes) {
    if (strings.size() > 1) {
        totalColisoas += (strings.size() - 1);

        // Displays the first 5 collisions found to avoid flooding the screen
        if (totalColisoas <= 5) {
            cout << "Hash: [" << hash << "] collided for inputs: ";
            for (const string& s : strings) {
                cout << "\"" << s << "\" ";
            }
            cout << endl;
        }
    }
}

cout << "-----" << endl;
cout << "Total collisions detected: " << totalColisoas << endl;
taxaColisao = (static_cast<double>(totalColisoas) / totalStringsTestadas) * 100.0;
cout << "Collision rate within the tested scope: " << taxaColisao << "%" << endl;
cout << "=====" << endl;

cout << endl << "Press <Enter> to exit... ";
cin.get();

return 0;
}

```